

Amplifying Awareness: The Media's Role in Environmental Advocacy in Iraq

Mohammed Satar Saeed¹, Ali Mohammed Salih*², Rawezh Kamaran Ahmed³, Hataw Hussein³, Yohan Othman Hama⁴, Kamaran Qader Yaqub⁵

¹Department of Islamic study, Imam Aldham University.

²Department of Petroleum and Energy, Technical College of Engineering, Sulaimani Polytechnic University.

³Department of Media, College of Human Science, University of Halabja.

⁴Media Department, College of Humanities, University of Sulaimani.

⁵Department of Accounting, Technical College of Administration, Sulaimani Polytechnic University

ABSTRACT

Media plays an important role for creating environment awareness among society and can reduce the risks. This paper focuses on the role of media in enhancement of environmental awareness and evaluate the role which media plays in enhancing environmental awareness by serving as a powerful platform to disseminate information, influence public opinion, and drive positive change. Increasing environmental awareness is crucial for fostering a sense of responsibility and encouraging sustainable practices among individuals and publics. This research explores the critical role of media in enhancing environmental awareness in Iraq. By examining traditional and digital media platforms, the study highlights how these channels inform the public about environmental issues, influence policy-making, and foster community engagement. The findings suggest that an informed public is essential for effective environmental advocacy, and the media serves as a vital conduit for information dissemination.

Keywords: Environmental Awareness, Environmental Issues, Media, pollution, Circuit communication

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution can effects on ecosystems, human health, quality of daily life and natural environment. Therefor addressing these environmental crises requires internal and international coordination efforts (United Nations Environment Programme). To improve environment actions, need to be implemented such as proper managements, sustainable development practices, long-term strategic plan, conservation measures, the implementation of cleaner technologies, and imply the international climate change agreements, such as the Paris Agreement (Environmental Pollution Control Measures and Strategies: An Overview, 2023). While more work, need to be performed including review governmental policy, education and society awareness against environmental issues (Salih et al. 2025; Abdulrahman et al., 2025; Fatah et al., 2025; Mohammed et al., 2025). Iraq are facing several environmental issues such as population growth, poor

air quality, poor land use planning, the impact of three wars, climate change, and encroachment on fragile ecosystems (World Bank, 2017). The major causes of pollution are increased due to manmade activities. If necessary action not taken seriously, it would destroy ecosystem and effect public health (Al-Shammari, 2015; Omar et al., 2025; Rahman et al., 2025). The awareness for environment protection needs to take place as an important feature among the public through media. Environmental awareness in Iraq has been an growing issue, with numerous challenges related to contamination, water scarcity, immigration, overpopulation, deforestation, and the impacts of climate change (Al-Shammari, 2015; Palani et al., 2025). This risk can be reduced, by raise awareness among Iraqi's citizens through media and address these concerns as a quick solution. Among Iraqi society, the media plays a vital role in raising environmental awareness via influencing public

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

opinion, and fostering positive change. Through media, can reach a widespread of audience and convey information in various subjects makes it an essential partner in global efforts to address environmental challenges (Rahim and Jalaladeen, 2015). Therefore, the media can be a powerful tool used for proceeding environmental awareness. It not only educates the communities but also encouraging individuals and public people to take positive action. By creating extensive awareness, inducing policy decisions, and promotion a culture of sustainability, the media supports significantly to global policy efforts towards preservative the environment for future generations (Saneh, 2018). Environmental awareness and education is growing gradually in Iraq, while the country faces significant and serious challenges in managing its natural resources sustainably(Salih et al., 2025). There is a need for more education, awareness, environmental protection policy development, and global collaboration to address the environmental issues and guarantee a better quality of life for Iraq's people. The aim of this paper is to explore the role of media in increasing environmental awareness among Iraqi society. The media serves another important purpose: increasing public awareness of environmental issues. The greater the public's awareness, the more intense the debate becomes, leading to potential solutions (Saneh, 2018). While traditional print media continues to contribute to community awareness through a well-defined agenda, new media including the internet and social platforms have a significant impact on younger audiences. Unlike newspapers, which can be revisited, information on television and social networks is often brief and transient. Nonetheless, both traditional and digital media are crucial in promoting environmental awareness (Rahim and Jalaladeen 2015). As the public becomes more informed about environmental matters, it demands the creation and enforcement of policies aimed at protecting nature and the environment. Change in the surrounding environment is something conflicts with sociality and affects daily life. Up to date, several environmental crises and challenges were ongoing which refers to the introduction of harmful contaminants into the environment, causing adverse effects. Thus, increasing environmental awareness is crucial for fostering a sense of responsibility and encouraging sustainable practices among individuals

and publics. This article investigates the influence of various media forms on environmental advocacy and public perception in Iraq.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing literature emphasizes the media's function in shaping public discourse on environmental issues. Studies show that countries with robust media engagement tend to have higher levels of environmental awareness and proactive policy responses. The following section examines pertinent studies on the impact of media in environmental contexts, specifically focusing on Iraq.

2.1. Role of Media as a Environmental Advocacy Tool

The influence of media on community awareness and policy agendas has carefully observed in previous studies. According to recent findings, McCombs and Shaw's (1972) Agenda-Setting Theory suggests that media effects public perception by highlighting a real issues in related with environmental advocacy. Media plays a crucial role by translating multifaceted scientific information into accessible and understandable for the public (Cox, 2013). Previous studies indicate that effective media attention can assemble public support, effect policy decisions, and promote general action on environmental issues (Boykoff, 2011). Iraq is facing various environmental challenges including water scarcity, pollution, overpopulation, random deforestation, climate migrants, intensive agriculture and climate change are becoming more demanding. The role of media is particularly significant and effectiveness to effect political, economic, and social problems. Various media channels, including television, radio, print, and digital platforms, disseminate information on environmental issues like climate change, deforestation, pollution, and biodiversity loss.

2.2. Environmental Challenges in Iraq

Iraq faces a various environmental challenges, which have exaggerated by years of war, poor governance policy, and insufficient infrastructure (Salih et al. 2021). Natural resource management in Iraq is a significant concern due to the country's abundant resources, such as oil, gas, water, and agricultural land (Salih et al., 2018; Yaqub et al., 2024). Effective

management is essential for achieving sustainable development, encourage economic growth, and protecting the ecosystem and human health . With the fifth-largest proven oil reserves globally, oil is a essential element of Iraq's economy. Effective resources management is essential for producing revenue and proceeding national development (Salih et al., 2020). The Tigris and Euphrates rivers accented as the primary natural sources of freshwater, which are important for both agriculture and drinking water. However, water management faces several challenges, including pollution, over-extraction, and regional wars (Yaqub et al., 2024; Salih et al. 2025). The Tigris and Euphrates rivers, vital for Iraq's ecosystem and agriculture, have experienced diminished flows due to upstream damming in Turkey and Iran (UNEP, 2019). Oil spills, industrial waste, and lack of waste water management have resulted in significant soil and water contamination (Al-Ansari, 2021; Salih et al., 2019). Increasing temperatures, reduced rainfall, higher evaporation rates and desertification pose threats to food security and livelihoods, especially in rural regions (World Bank, 2020). Agriculture plays a key role in ensuring food security and employs a large portion of the population, but it also confronts issues such as soil degradation, water scarcity, and outdated agricultural practices. Despite these pressing issues, public awareness of environmental problems remains low, partly due to insufficient media coverage and educational efforts (Al-Delaimy, 2020).

3. Role of Media in Promoting Environment Awareness in Iraq

The media plays a crucial role in shaping public awareness of global climate change and related actions. The media's role are focusing on three main aspects: informing, educating, and entertaining (Saneh, 2018). Traditionally, tools like local radio, television, and newspapers have been instrumental in

spreading awareness about climate change and environmental protections well as printed materials, including books, magazines, and brochures, had contributed to the dissemination of new and information about natural disasters such as earthquakes, volcanic activity, landslides, drought, wildfires, storms, and flooding (Dave, 2014). Nowadays satellites television are vital for delivering quick updates, while social media is more critical role among the Iraqi society. Iraq's media setting is complex and fragmented, influenced by the political transformations before and after since 2003. The rise of independent and digital media outlets has allowed for a variety of perspectives, but challenges such as censorship, political meddling, and resource shortages persist (Zanger and Al-Rawi, 2017). Environmental reporting often takes a backseat to more immediate political and security matters, leading to sporadic and limited coverage (Abdul-Zahra, 2018). In early 2004, Iraq experienced a significant expansion in its media landscape, with the licensing of over 200 daily or weekly newspapers, 80 radio stations, and 20 television channels. This period also saw the spread of satellite dishes across the rooftops of Iraqi homes, marking a new era of media accessibility. According to official statistics published in early 2022 by the Iraqi Media Authority, Iraq currently hosts 55 licensed radio stations and 37 satellite channels, along with 40 companies and media offices. Additionally, the Iraqi Journalists Syndicate reported in 2014-2015 that there were 110 FM radio stations, 11 AM radio stations, and 25 digital media outlets registered in the country. These developments reflect the growing influence and diversity of media in Iraq, facilitating broader access to information across various platforms (UNDP Iraq Citizen Journalism Project, 2023). Figure(1) provided a pie chart that illustrates the number of licensed media channels in Iraq for 2022, featuring categories like radio stations, media companies/offices, and satellite channels.

Figure 1: Illustrates the number of licensed media channels in Iraq for 2022 (UNDP Iraq Citizen Journalism Project, 2023).

Digital media, particularly social platforms, has emerged as a powerful means for grassroots environmental advocacy in Iraq. Platforms like Facebook and Twitter enable activists to circumvent traditional media barriers and rally support for environmental issues (Al-Mahmood, 2022). However, the effectiveness of digital campaigns is often restricted by low internet access in rural areas and the prevalence of misinformation. The media conveys complex environmental information in a manner that is easy for the public to access and understand. It is essential for media professionals to present scientific and academic data through various formats, such as news reports, documentaries, and educational programs, transforming scientific research into practical knowledge. Due to power of globalization, media outlets frequently address environmental issues on both local and global scales, which is highlighting and interconnected environmental challenges (Khan and Khan, 2020). This approach helps the Iraqi community to recognize the global consequences of their actions and lifestyle, such as how local pollution impacts climate change. Bellow summaries how media can contributes towards raising awareness about environmental issues:

3.1. Education and Knowledge Distribution

Media channels, such as social media, newspapers, satellites, television, radio, and online website, are essential for rising awareness and educating the public toward environmental issues. They deliver wide-

ranging of attention, research understandings, and expert perceptions to notify audiences about global warming, climate change, waste managements, water managements, biodiversity loss, and other environmental conditions, (Saneh, 2018).

3.2. Environmental Issues Documentary Report

Through documentaries, investigative journalism, and graphic storytelling, the media highlights environmental challenges nationally and globally. By display casing real-life stories, real images, and videos, the media makes multifaceted subjects more accessible and understandable to a wider audience, fostering empathy and concern (Silva and Lima, 2023).

3.3. Public Campaigns for Sustainable Practices

Television advertisements, social media campaigns, and online content encourage people to adopt environmentally friendly practices, including minimizing waste and plastic consumption, lowering carbon dioxide emissions, preserving water, and using renewable energy sources (Sustainability, 2023).

3.4. Involving Experts in the Dialogue

The media serves as a platform for environmentalists, scientists, and academics to share their insights and research, fostering credibility around environmental issues and providing the public with access to expert viewpoints. Documentaries and interviews with environmental scientists featured on major news

networks enhance understanding by illustrating the current conditions of ecosystems and wildlife (Cockerill, 2002).

3.5. Social Media as a Universal Tool

As social media usage grows globally as well as among the Iraqi society, thus information about environmental issues can be swiftly shared with both local and global audiences. Online platforms facilitate the dissemination of awareness, news, educational materials, and user-generated discussions, creating a sense of global environmental community and

activism (Rahim and Jalaladeen, 2016). Social media supports viral campaigns that can quickly gain international attention. These platforms promote user participation, making environmental activism more accessible and widespread. They also provide spaces for individuals to brainstorm, share sustainable solutions, and engage in global conversations on pressing environmental issues. Figure (2) illustrating the number of social media users in Iraq between 2018 and 2024, featuring platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, Messenger, TikTok, LinkedIn, and YouTube.

Figure 2: illustrating the number of social media users in Iraq between 2018 and 2024, featuring platforms

3.6. Influencing Government and Involve Policymakers

Media coverage can shape public opinion, which in turn can sway policymakers and legislators to prioritize environmental concerns. By keeping environmental issues in the public eye, the media plays a significant role in helping to develop policies and regulations aimed at tackling environmental challenges. The media plays a crucial role in holding governments and corporations accountable for their environmental actions. Investigative journalism and coverage of detrimental corporate practices often provoke public outrage and push for policy reforms (Cockerill, 2002). Media helps companies recognize the public's demand for sustainability, often leading them to adopt greener practices due to scrutiny and heightened consumer awareness.

3.7. Performing with an Environmental Memorandum

Films and documentaries combine entertainment with education, emotionally connecting with audiences and highlighting the urgency of environmental protection. Fictional works, Television shows, films and movies frequently explore environmental themes, occasionally portraying dystopian futures caused by environmental degradation (Moser and Dilling, 2011). These stories can foster creativity and stimulate discussions about real-world environmental challenges.

3.8. Crisis Response and Disaster Reporting

Throughout the environmental disasters, the media can paly crucial role for delivering real-time updates, raising awareness of the situation, and mobilizing support for relief initiatives. Accurate and actual reporting is also vital for ensuring accountable those responsible for environmental crises. (Cockerill, 2002).

4. Comparative Analysis of Media

Comparative research on media-driven environmental advocacy in conflict-affected countries such as Syria and Yemen offers important insights. For example, Al-Saleh (2020) points out that Syrian activists have utilized social media to raise awareness of water pollution caused by conflict. Similarly, Yemeni journalists have used digital platforms to document the environmental consequences of war, even while confronting significant dangers (Al-Zikri, 2021). These cases illustrate the media's potential as an advocacy tool for environmental issues in difficult situations, while also highlighting the risks and limitations involved. As previously mentioned, this study observes media coverage of environmental issues. For this purpose, six Iraqi television channels analyzed through their websites over a two-month period (January and February 2025).

- **Al-Iraqiya TV:** A review of Al-Iraqiya TV's archives for these two months revealed minimal attention to environmental issues, with only two articles addressing local environmental topics, both related to current local events
- **Al-Rasheed TV:** An examination of the Al-Rasheed TV website archives for the same period showed limited coverage of environmental issues, with just one article on the subject.
- **Al-Sumaria News TV:** A search of the archives on Al-Sumaria News TV's website during the selected timeframe uncovered 16 articles focused on various environmental topics, including 11 news reports and two television segments dedicated to environmental issues.
- **Gali Kurdistan TV:** A search of the archives on the Gali Kurdistan Television website for the designated two-month period revealed four journalistic articles. Three of these were news pieces: one covering the signing of a memorandum of understanding between President Jalal Talabani's institution and the Iraqi Ministry of Environment, another discussing the environmental cost of electric vehicles, and a program also focusing on the same issue surrounding electric vehicles.
- **Kurdistan 24 TV:** A search on the Kurdistan 24 website for the specified period uncovered 75

journalistic articles addressing various environmental issues. These articles consisted mainly of news reports as well as television reports. Out of the total, 65 were news reports, while the rest were television field reports.

- **Rudaw:** During the two months (January and February 2025), Rudaw published 76 journalistic articles on various environmental topics. Most of these were field coverage news reports, followed by press releases and announcements.

Coverage of environmental issues on selected Iraqi television channels, especially Arabic in Baghdad, remains minimal. It is worth mentioning that there were no programs or advertisements that focused on environmental protection during this period. At the same time, we tried to do more research on environmental issues on both our Kurdish and Arabic websites. Looked at all major website categories, including Local, Politics, Security, Economy, World, Arab International, Diversity, Sports, Women, Weather News, Horoscope, and Science and Technology. Unfortunately, however, none of the websites included an "environment" section as a special section.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the media plays an essential role in raising environmental awareness, influencing behaviors, and facilitating positive change. Its ability to reach a broad audience and present information in various formats makes it a crucial ally in global efforts to address environmental issues. Although research on media and environmental advocacy is growing, few studies specifically focus on Iraq. Much of the existing literature emphasizes political and security issues, leaving environmental topics relatively neglected. Additionally, there is a lack of empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of media campaigns in promoting environmental policy changes in Iraq. This disparity underscores the necessity for more focused research to improve awareness initiatives related to environmental protection. It can be concluded that media plays a crucial role in environmental advocacy, especially in country such as Iraq, where environmental issues interlink with political and social complications. Meanwhile, while digital media creates new

opportunities and modern pathways for public activism, traditional media faces structural limitations. Future research should investigate how media can be utilized to enhance environmental awareness and promote policy changes in Iraq, using theoretical frameworks like framing theory and development communication. Although environmental awareness is about to rise, Iraq struggles with the sustainable management of its natural resources. There is an emergency need for improved education, environmental policy development, and international collaboration to face environmental challenges and enhance the quality of life in Iraq and world.

REFERENCE

1. "Antioxidant: A review of their chemistry and biology" (Journal of agricultural and food chemistry, 2018, vol.66, no.2, pp.533-542). "The role of antioxidant in human health" (Journal of Nutrition and Metabolism, 2020, vol.23, pp.1-11).
2. "A comparative study of in vitro antioxidant assays" (Food chemistry) Evaluation of antioxidant activity of plant extracts in vitro assays" (Journal of food science)
3. "In vitro antioxidant assays: a review of the current status" (Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology, 2020)
4. "Antioxidant activity of plant extract" (Journal of agricultural and food chemistry, 2018, vol.66, no.2, pp.533-542).
5. "In vitro antioxidant assays: A review" (Journal of Agricultural and food chemistry, 2018, vol.66, no.2, pp.533-542).
6. Carlsen, M. H., et al. (2010). "The total antioxidant content of more than 3100 foods, beverages, spices, herbs and supplements used worldwide." *Nutrition Journal*, 9(1), 1-11.
7. "Alam, Md Nur, Nusrat Jahan Bristi, and Md Rafiquzzaman." "Review on in vivo and in vitro methods evaluation of antioxidant activity." *Saudi pharmaceutical journal* 21, no. 2 (2013): 143-152.
8. "Garg, S., Garg, A., Shukla, A., Dev, S. K., Bishnoi, R. S., & Kumar, M." (2018). Review on antioxidant evaluation methods: And models In-vitro in-vivo. *Asian J. Pharm. Pharmacol*, 4, 147-154.
9. Madhuranga, H. D. T., and D. N. A. W. Samarakoon. "In Vitro anti-inflammatory egg albumin denaturation assay." *Methodology* (2023): 1-5
10. Alam, M.N., Bristi, N.J. and Rafiquzzaman, M., 2013. Review on in vivo and in vitro methods evaluation of antioxidant activity. *Saudi pharmaceutical journal*, 21(2), pp.143-152.
11. Nm, J. O. S. E. P. H., Sabharwal Monika, Shashi Alok, Mahor Alok, and Rawal Shruti. "In vitro and in vivo models for antioxidant activity evaluation: A review." *Int J Pharm Sci Res* 1, no. 1 (2010): 1-11.
12. Chanda, S., and R. Dave. "In vitro models for antioxidant activity evaluation and some medicinal plants possessing antioxidant properties: An overview." *African Journal of Microbiology Research* 3, no. 13 (2009): 981-996.
13. Premanath, Ramya, and N. Lakshmidivi. "Studies on anti-oxidant activity of *Tinospora cordifolia* (Miers.) leaves using in vitro models." *Journal of American science* 6, no. 10 (2010): 736-743

HOW TO CITE: Mohammed Satar Saeed, Ali Mohammed Salih*, Rawezh Kamaran Ahmed, Hataw Hussein, Yohan Othman Hama, Kamaran Qader Yaqub, Amplifying Awareness: The Media's Role in Environmental Advocacy in Iraq, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (3), 618-624. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105484>